

EDUCATIONAL APPS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS: EXPLORING PERCEPTIONS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

¹Nida Shahzad, ²Muhammad Kazim, ³Ayaz Ahmed

¹Virtual University of Pakistan

²National University of Modern Languages

³Virtual University of Pakistan

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords

Educational Apps, Teaching of Mathematics, Teachers Perceptions, Benefits & Challenges

Article History

Received on 09 July 2025

Accepted on 06 Aug 2025

Published on 08 Aug 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

The study aimed to explore the use of educational apps in Mathematics and perceptions of primary school teachers' regarding this innovative approach. The sample of the study was primary school teachers from Rawalpindi city. The study highlighted the benefits, challenges and influencing factors that affect teachers' decisions regarding usage of educational apps for teaching Mathematics. The results of the study indicated that primary school teachers are having positive perceptions about usage of these apps but, they also highlighted several challenges such as technical issues, inadequate training, difficulties in curriculum alignment and less confidence of teachers in using technology that needs to be addressed to get maximum benefit from the apps. It is recommended to provide better internet access, enough technology based resources and proper technical training to teachers for utilizing educational apps effectively.

INTRODUCTION

Technology has emerged as a most vital part of the modern society; it has effected all educational areas including subjects like Mathematics. Educational apps can be a good tool to make mathematics more engaging subject for students specially at primary school level. These apps are beneficial along with traditional teaching because of engaging and interactive content that can be used to cater various learning needs and styles of the students (Madawistama et al., 2024). Teachers can enhance mathematical proficiency and understanding of students by utilizing digital apps in the primary schools of Rawalpindi. Teachers are the implementers of educational apps within the class that is why their perceptions regarding utilization of apps for teaching Mathematics is essential for effectively implementing and optimizing these resources in the primary schools.

Educational apps have a potential to improve students learning and engagement in mathematics classes but, particularly in Rawalpindi there is limited research exploring teachers' perceptions and experiences regarding the use of digital apps in primary education. There is a need to understand teachers' attitudes, beliefs, and practices regarding the integration of educational apps into mathematics instruction to utilize these resources more effectively and overcome any challenges or barriers blocking the effective usage of these apps.

It is necessary to understand that to what extent teachers are comfortable in utilizing technology-based apps, what is their skill level regarding that, how do they perceive the role of technology in the classroom and its utilization along with traditional teaching approaches. Additionally, investigating the factors influencing teachers' decisions to adopt or resist the use of educational apps in mathematics instruction can provide valuable insights into designing targeted interventions and professional development programs to support teachers in leveraging these resources effectively. Furthermore, the best practices and strategies utilized by the teachers who successfully incorporated educational apps into their mathematics classes can be shared with other teachers within the Rawalpindi and beyond. Overall, it will contribute in the improvement of the mathematics education for primary school students. This study aims to explore the perceptions of teachers regarding the use of educational apps to teach mathematics, identifying the perceived benefits and challenges of using educational apps to teach mathematics and examining the factors influencing teachers' decision to use educational apps in mathematics instruction in primary schools of Rawalpindi.

LITERATURE REVIEW

For enhancing students' learning, utilization of mobile devices like Tablet PCs or iPads in educational settings has been identified as an effective strategy (Banister, 2010; Bonds-Raacke & Raacke, 2015; Enriquez, 2010). Ifenthaler and Schweinbenz, 2013 indicated in their study that these technology-based devices are beneficial due to their multiple interesting and valuable features like access to tools like cameras and microphones, fast internet connectivity, increasing computational capabilities, and high-quality graphics. Due to these features these devices can be effectively used in multiple forms of technology-based instructions like game-based learning, blended learning, collaborative learning and student-centered learning (Ludwig, Mayrberger & Weidmann, 2011). Utilization of educational apps for teaching of mathematics is getting much attention (Amin, 2010; Banister, 2010; Moreau, 2010; Ross, Morrison, & Lowther, 2010). In addition to this, multiple researches Alagic, 2013, Berk, 2010, Hamilton, 2017, Mendicino, Heffernan & Razaq, 2017, Park, 2018 and Rosen & Beck-Hill, 2012 has indicated the positive relationship among the usage of technology-based devices and learning outcomes for the subject of mathematics.

The focus of today's modern teaching approaches is more on involving students in the lesson instead of treating them as empty vessels. Game-based learning is more student-centered and gaining popularity because of its capacity to engage students and making learning enjoyable for them (Razak, Connolly, & Hainey, 2012). Further, Barab et al., 2015 also indicated that game-based learning refers to educational activities that captivate learners' attention by involving them in gameplay during lessons that is why it is better to inculcate them during math's classes to get maximum benefits. Different researchers devised and utilized educational games such as Quest Atlantis using Scratch and commercially available role-playing game (Civilization) and get positive results in-terms of students' outcomes (Barab et al., 2015 & Squire, 2013). Since then, numerous technologies have been integrated into classrooms to enhance students' mathematical proficiency and foster their engagement.

For differentiated learning teachers can effectively utilize educational apps in their classrooms by utilizing tablets or computers because it has a capacity of customization to fulfil individual student's needs (Álvarez Domínguez et al., 2024). This will also facilitate teachers to utilize both synchronous and asynchronous activities along with prompt assessment and feedback for improving students learning. These benefits highlight the significance of

recognizing and valuing educational apps for modern educators, thereby forming essential considerations while considering the application of educational apps in mathematical classes.

Previous studies indicated that educational apps have a capacity to significantly improve students' diverse skills such as early literacy skills including phonological awareness, recognizing alphabets and development of vocabulary. Further, use of digital technologies particularly educational apps can also improve language proficiency among children (Abisheva & Mirza, 2024). Multiple literacy apps are linked with improving child language proficiency both in native and foreign languages (Papadakis & Kalogiannakis, 2019). Educational apps are beneficial not only because it provides immediate access to information and learning but also contributing in promoting social interactions, developing problem-solving skills through involving students in inquiry, enhancing active participation, sharing of ideas, data collection, data analysis and interpreting results (Haleem et al., 2022). This indicates that educational apps are effectively contributing in wide range of skills development among students, a fact widely recognized by education experts and researchers.

Despite its advantages, the integration of innovative classroom technology often faces pedagogical challenges (Ferguson & Oigara, 2017). Constraints such as curriculum limitations, class duration, class size, physical space for activities, teacher proficiency, and student readiness to embrace technology can impede its effective use in instruction (Gómez-Fernández & Mediavilla, 2022; Johnson et al., 2016).

However, the adoption of instructional technology by teachers remains relatively limited compared to the abundance of technology present in modern classrooms (Kopcha, 2012). This is especially notable considering that most teachers primarily utilize technology for administrative tasks such as grading, assigning homework, managing attendance, or facilitating communication with school staff or parents (Kopcha, 2012). Without active involvement from teachers in utilizing technology in the classroom, successful integration of educational apps into the learning process is unattainable (Ertmer, 2015).

It is necessary to explore teachers' perceptions regarding utilization of mobile learning and educational apps for teaching in the classroom so that we can identify and overcome the obstacles they face while implementing educational technology in the real classroom settings (Ifenthaler & Schweinbenz, 2013; Ertmer, 2015). Exploring teachers' attitudes toward educational apps is also crucial because teachers are the one who implement this technology

and until they are not having positive attitude they might not implement it effectively and understand the value of this approach. Moreover, teachers' beliefs and attitude can also impact students' engagement, interaction, and learning outcomes with digital tools.

There are very limited studies that focused on exploring the teachers' perception regarding utilization of educational apps specially for teaching mathematics leaves a gap to explore more about perspectives of teachers regarding benefits, barriers, and concerns associated with integrating them into educational settings.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There is growing international concern about the levels of participation and success rates of learners in mathematics, particularly in developed countries (Noyes & Sealey, 2012). The state of mathematics education in developing nations warrants even greater concern. However, the situation in South Africa (SA) is particularly troubling, where the performance of learners in mathematics ranks as the lowest among all middle-income countries globally and even worse than many low-income African countries, according to international studies (McCarthy & Oliphant, 2013). The authors believe that all stakeholders must prioritize investigating innovative methods that could enhance the mathematics performance of school learners in their communities. Educational experts suggest that providing learners with information and communication technology (ICT) solutions could be one approach to improving mathematics performance (Haleem et al., 2022). Regarding the use of ICT solutions in mathematics teaching, several researchers concur on the benefits it offers. Baya'a and Daher (2013) conclude that the integration of ICT in mathematics education equips mathematics teachers with integrative teaching methods that support learners' independent learning. Specifically, Subramanya and Farahani (2012) have identified several key benefits of mobile apps for learning mathematics concepts, including self-paced learning, reinforcement of abstract concepts, supplemental learning aids, anytime/anywhere use, enhanced retention, entertainment and engagement, utilization of multiple media formats, immersion in interaction, self-assessment, exploration and experimentation opportunities, provision of positive feedback, cost-effectiveness, customizability, and time-effectiveness. Prensky (2012) contends that mobile educational apps represent some of the most valuable learning tools ever created and are preferable to traditional learning tools like books and laptops. Another significant potential learning benefit of mobile apps, as identified by Kheirzadeh and

Malakootikhah (2023) is the repetitive use of content, enabling weaker learners to repeatedly practice difficult concepts.

An examination of literature pertaining to the perceptions of teachers toward mobile technologies for learning reveals that these perceptions evolve over time. A study conducted by Druin (2019) indicated that parents and teachers held negative views regarding the educational value of mobile technologies, perceiving cell phones as distractions unsuitable for school settings. In contrary to this, another study claimed that 70% of teachers believed that tablet devices offer new learning opportunities that are not achievable with current teaching methods or tools (Hopkins, 2016). In addition, Ferry (2018) concluded in his study that majority of the Nigerian secondary schools has imposed ban on utilization of mobile phones within the school premises due to concerns over students spending excessive time chatting, viewing inappropriate content such as pornography, and engaging in recording irrelevant or violent activities. It indicates that mobile devices can be both helpful and disruptive in school settings due to improper usage and inadequate supervision, the aim of such bans is to foster improved moral behavior and academic performance among students.

Despite these negative viewpoints, we still need to explore the perceptions of teachers regarding the potential use of mobile applications as learning tools in Mathematics because we cannot overlook the positive impact of m-learning on the teaching and learning of Mathematics. Attention must be directed towards examining the patterns of m-Apps usage among teachers and students in secondary schools, including the purposes, utilization methods, and factors influencing m-Apps usage. Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to evaluate the perceptions of teachers regarding the use of mobile applications in the teaching and learning of Mathematics in primary schools of Rawalpindi. This study is anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which anticipates and elucidates the reasons behind user acceptance or rejection of computer-based innovations (Davis, 1986; Silva, 2015;).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the quantitative approach. Survey design was used for data collection and for analysis descriptive design was used. This approach was selected to systematically gather numerical data and statistically analyze the perceptions of teachers regarding the use of educational apps to teach mathematics to primary school students in Rawalpindi.

Teachers of primary schools in the city of Rawalpindi were considered as the Population of the study. This population was chosen to provide a broad and inclusive sample that could offer insights into the varying perceptions and experiences of teachers from different schools and backgrounds within the city. Focusing on primary school teachers the importance was given to the teachers of early mathematics education. A purposive and stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from different schools, both public and private, within Rawalpindi. Schools were first categorized based on their type and location, and then teachers were randomly selected from each category. This approach helped to minimize sampling bias and ensured that the sample accurately represented the diverse population of primary school teachers in Rawalpindi. The sample size for the study consisted of n=200 primary school teachers. This sample size was determined by using the Google sample calculator.

Structured questionnaire based on five-point likert scale options was utilized to get perceptions of primary school teachers. The questionnaire was carefully designed to gather detailed information about teachers' perceptions of educational apps, their usage frequency, perceived effectiveness, any challenges faced and influences on decision-making. The reliability of the tool was .856.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The questionnaire was prepared online on Google forms and the link was distributed among the teachers. This study was descriptive in nature so percentages were calculated for each construct by using SPSS.

BENEFITS OF EDUCATIONAL APPS FOR MATHEMATICS TEACHING AND LEARNING

TABLE 1: *BENEFITS OF EDUCATIONAL APPS FOR MATHEMATICS TEACHING AND LEARNING.*

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The teacher believes educational apps enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts.	1.0	89.2	2.0	4.9	2.9
The teacher believes that educational apps	2.0	89.2	2.9	3.9	2.0

help in maintaining students' interest in mathematics.

The teacher finds educational apps to be an effective tool for teaching mathematics. 1.0 77.5 2.9 5.9 12.5

The teacher thinks educational apps improve students' problem-solving skills. 1.0 77.5 3.9 7.8 9.8

The teacher feels that using educational apps makes mathematics instruction more interactive. 1.0 91.2 2.9 2.9 2.0

The teacher perceives educational apps as a valuable addition to traditional teaching methods. 1.0 5.9 2.9 77.5 12.7

The construct of *Benefits of educational Apps for Mathematics Teaching and Learning* is consisted of six statements. The analysis of the results indicated that teachers showed agreement towards the five statements which indicates that as per teacher's perceptions educational apps can enhance the students' understanding of mathematical concepts, it helps in maintaining students' interest in mathematics, it can be an effective tool for teaching mathematics, it can improve students problem-solving skills and educational apps can make mathematics instructions more interactive.

Whereas, the analysis also indicated the disagreement of teachers towards one statement 'The teacher perceives educational apps as a valuable addition to traditional teaching methods'. It indicates that they do not think that it is a valuable addition to traditional teaching method, the reasons can be explored in future study.

USAGE OF EDUCATIONAL APPS FOR TEACHING MATHEMATICS

TABLE 2: USAGE OF EDUCATIONAL APPS FOR TEACHING MATHEMATICS.

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The teacher feels confident in using educational apps to teach mathematics.	1.0	4.9	2.9	81.4	9.8
The teacher integrates educational apps regularly into mathematics lessons.	2.9	2.9	2.9	89.2	2.0

The teacher believes that educational apps are accessible and easy to use for all students.

The construct of *Usage of Educational Apps for Teaching Mathematics* is consisted of three statements. Respondents showed disagreement towards all of the three statements which indicates that according to them they do not feel confident in using educational apps to teach mathematics, they do not integrate educational apps regularly into mathematics lessons and educational apps are not easily accessible and easy to use for all students.

CHALLENGES IN USING EDUCATIONAL APPS FOR MATHEMATICS

TABLE 3: *CHALLENGES IN USING EDUCATIONAL APPS FOR MATHEMATICS.*

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The teacher encounters technical issues when using educational apps in the classroom.	1.0	92.2	2.0	3.9	1.0
The teacher feels that there is inadequate training on how to effectively use educational apps.	2.0	88.2	2.0	6.9	1.0
The teacher finds it challenging to integrate educational apps into the existing curriculum.	1.0	80.4	3.9	3.9	10.8
The teacher believes that educational apps require too much preparation time.	2.0	92.2	2.9	2.0	1.0

The construct of *Challenges in Using Educational Apps for Mathematics* is consisted of four statements. Respondents showed agreement towards all of the four statements indicating that as per their opinion there are multiple challenges associated with using educational apps for mathematics which are technical issues, inadequate training on how to effectively use educational apps, it is challenging to integrate educational apps into the existing curriculum and educational apps require too much preparation time on the behalf of the teacher.

INFLUENCING FACTORS FOR DECISION-MAKING

TABLE 4: *INFLUENCING FACTORS FOR DECISION-MAKING*

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by the availability of technological resources.	1.0	80.4	2.9	4.9	10.8
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by the perceived effectiveness of the apps.	2.0	80.4	2.9	3.9	10.8
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by students' enthusiasm for technology.	2.0	81.4	3.9	2.9	9.8
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by peer recommendations.	2.0	80.4	4.9	2.9	9.8
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by administrative support.	2.9	83.3	2.9	2.9	7.8
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by the cost of the apps.	2.9	90.2	3.9	2.0	1.0
The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by professional development opportunities.	2.0	89.2	2.0	5.9	1.0

The construct of *Influencing Factors for Decision-Making* is consisted of seven statements. Respondents showed agreement towards all of the statements indicating that The teacher's decision to use educational apps is influenced by the availability of technological resources, perceived effectiveness of the apps, students' enthusiasm for technology, peers' recommendations, administrative support, cost of the apps and professional development opportunities.

FINDINGS

- Teachers in Rawalpindi generally perceive educational apps as beneficial for enhancing students' understanding of mathematical concepts. They recognize the value of these apps in making mathematics instruction more interactive and engaging.
- Significant number of teachers do not feel confident in using educational apps to teach mathematics, they do not integrate educational apps regularly into mathematics lessons however, the extent of usage varies depending on the availability of resources and the teacher's familiarity with the technology.
- Teachers believe that educational apps help maintain students' interest in mathematics, improve problem-solving skills, and make lessons more interactive. Whereas, analysis also indicated that teachers do not think educational apps as valuable addition to traditional teaching methods of Mathematics.
- Technical issues, inadequate training, difficulty in integrating apps into the existing curriculum, and the significant preparation time required are common concerns highlighted by the teachers.
- The availability of technological resources, the perceived effectiveness of the apps, students' enthusiasm for technology, peer recommendations, administrative support, cost considerations, and professional development opportunities were highlighted as the factors that influence the decision to use educational apps within the class

DISCUSSIONS

The study highlights that primary school teachers in Rawalpindi generally have positive perceptions of educational apps for teaching mathematics. They claimed that educational apps are beneficial for enhancing student engagement and understanding of mathematical concepts. These results are akin with the previous study (Subramanya & Farahani, 2012). In addition to this, study revealed technical issues, such as unreliable internet connections and software glitches, as major obstacles that hinder the effective integration of educational apps into mathematics instruction Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2010) also confirm these results. Further, it has been indicated that teachers' confidence level regarding utilization of educational apps is quiet low because they find it challenging to utilize properly, these results

are similar to previous studies (Hegedus et al., 2017). Moreover, many teachers feel that they lack adequate training on how to use these apps effectively, which affects their confidence and willingness to incorporate them into their lessons (Johnson et al., 2016). Furthermore, teachers find it hard to seamlessly integrate app-based activities into their lesson plans without disrupting the flow of traditional instructions. The difficulty in aligning educational apps with the existing curriculum is another significant challenge confirmed by previous literature (Norton & Hathaway, 2015). Additionally, the preparation time required to set up and familiarize themselves with the apps is seen as a burden by many educators. In addition to this, factors influencing the decision to use educational apps are multifaceted. Access to technological resources is crucial, as schools with limited infrastructure struggle to implement these tools (Pelgrum, 2001). The perceived effectiveness of the apps and students' enthusiasm for using technology in learning are strong motivators for teachers confirmed by other studies (Qiu et al., 2022). Further, peer recommendations and administrative support play a critical role in encouraging teachers to adopt educational apps. However, cost considerations and the availability of professional development opportunities also significantly impact their decisions (Ching & Hursh, 2014).

CONCLUSION

It has been concluded that primary school teachers at Rawalpindi are having positive perceptions regarding the use of educational apps for teaching of Mathematics. They consider this approach as beneficial but also highlighted challenges that needs to be addressed to get maximum benefits. Teachers' confidence needs to be increased by providing professional development trainings. Similarly, technical issues, inadequate training, and curriculum alignment difficulties are significant barriers that must be overcome. To fully realize the benefits of educational apps, it is essential to provide adequate technological resources and ensure reliable internet connectivity in schools.

RECOMMENDATION

This study further recommends:

- Primary schools must invest in improving technological infrastructure in schools, ensuring reliable internet connectivity and access to necessary devices for both teachers and students.

- Developing and implementing comprehensive training programs for teachers, focusing on the effective use of educational apps in mathematics instruction.
- Continuous professional development opportunities should be provided to keep teachers updated on new technologies and teaching strategies.
- For integrating educational apps into existing lesson plans schools should involve teachers to collaborate with curriculum developers to create guidelines and resources. This will help teachers seamlessly incorporate app-based activities without disrupting the traditional flow of instruction.
- For resolving technical issues schools must establish a technical support system to assist teachers quickly and efficiently.
- Promote peer collaboration and knowledge-sharing among teachers through workshops, seminars, and online forums. Experienced teachers can share their best practices and successful strategies for using educational apps in mathematics instruction.
- Explore cost-effective solutions for acquiring educational apps, such as bulk licensing agreements, grants, or partnerships with app developers.
- Implement regular feedback mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of educational apps in mathematics instruction. Collect input from both teachers and students to identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to the implementation strategy

REFERENCES

- Abisheva, S., & Mirza, N. (2024). *Enhancing earlychildhood speech development through digital technologies: a systematic review. 1.* <https://doi.org/10.69927/bnfe5274>
- Alagic, M. (2013). Technology in the Mathematics Classroom: Conceptual Orientation. *Journal of Computers in Mathematics & Science Teaching*, 22(4), 381-399.
- Álvarez Domínguez, S., Macizo, P., Campos Vasquez, N., & Rodríguez, E. (2024). *The Influence of AI Apps on Enhancing Mathematics Learning Among Primary Education Students.* 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icacit62963.2024.10788650>
- Amin, J. (2010). Twenty First Century Classrooms: Changing Scenario. *Learning Community: An International Journal of Education & Social Development*, 1(1), 23-28.

- Banister, S. (2010). Integrating the iPod Touch in K-12 Education: Visions and Vices. *Computers in the Schools*, 27(2), 121-131.
- Barab, S., Thomas, M., Dodge, T., Carteaux, R., & Tuzun, H. (2015). Making learning fun: Quest Atlantis, a game without guns. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 53(1), 86-107.
- Baya'a, N., & Daher, W. (2013). Mathematics Teachers' Readiness to Integrate ICT in the Classroom. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 8(1).
- Berk, R. A. (2010). How Do You Leverage the Latest Technologies, including Web 2.0 Tools, in Your Classroom? *International Journal of Technology in Teaching and Learning*, 6(1), 1-13. Retrieved from http://www.ronberk.com/articles/2010_leverage.pdf
- Bonds-Raacke, J., & Raacke, J. D. (2015). Using Tablet PCs in the Classroom. An Investigation of Students' Expectations and Reactions. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 35(3), 235-239.
- Ching, C. C., & Hursh, A. W. (2014). Peer modeling and innovation adoption among teachers in online professional development. *Computers & Education*, 73, 72-82.
- Davis, F. D., (1986). A Technology Acceptance Model for Empirically Testing New End-User Information Systems. Theory and results. Dissertation. Sloan School of Management, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Enriquez, A. G. (2010). Enhancing Student Performance Using Tablet Computers. *College Teaching*, 58(3), 77-84.
- Ertmer, P. A. (2015). Teacher Pedagogical Beliefs: The Final Frontier in Our Quest for Technology Integration? *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 53(4), 25-39.
- Ferguson, J. M., & Oigara, J. N. (2017). iPads in the classroom: What do teachers think?. *International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education (IJICTE)*, 13(4), 74-86.
- Gómez-Fernández, N., & Mediavilla, M. (2022). Factors influencing teachers' use of ICT in class: evidence from a multilevel logistic model. *Mathematics*, 10(5), 799.
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable operations and computers*, 3, 275-285.

- Hamilton, B. (2017). *It's Elementary: Integrating Technology in the Primary Grades*. Eugene, OR: International Society for Technology in Education.
- Hegedus, S., Laborde, C., Brady, C., Dalton, S., Siller, H. S., Tabach, M., ... & Moreno-Armella, L. (2017). *Uses of technology in upper secondary mathematics education*. Springer Nature.
- Hopkins, P. (2016). Do tablets cure the pedagogy headache?. *Educational Futures*, 7(3).
- Ifenthaler, D. & Schweinbenz, V. (2013). The acceptance of Tablet-PCs in classroom instructions: The teachers' perspectives. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 525-534.
- Johnson, A. M., Jacovina, M. E., Russell, D. G., & Soto, C. M. (2016). Challenges and solutions when using technologies in the classroom. In *Adaptive educational technologies for literacy instruction* (pp. 13-30). Routledge.
- Kheirzadeh, S., & Malakootikhah, M. (2023). The Role of Content and Procedural Repetition in EFL Learners' Reading Performance. *Journal of College Reading and Learning*, 53(2), 131-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10790195.2022.2162464>
- Kopcha, T. J. (2012). Teachers' perceptions of the barriers to technology integration and practices with technology under situated professional development. *Computers & Education*, 59(4), 1109-1121.
- Ludwig, L., Mayrberger, K. & Weidmann, A. (2011). Einsatz personalisierter iPads im Unterricht aus Perspektive der Schülerinnen und Schüler. In S. Friedrich, A. Kienle & H. Rohland (Eds.), *DeLFI 2011: Die 9. e-Learning Fachtagung Informatik* (pp. 7-17).
- Madawistama, S. T., Wang, Y., Hayati, A., Wardhani, R. P., & Nurtamam, M. E. (2024). *Increasing Student Engagement through Mobile Learning in Mathematics Subjects*. <https://doi.org/10.70177/jssut.v2i1.782>
- Mendicino, M., Heffernan, N. T., & Razzaq, L. (2017). Comparing the learning from intelligent tutoring systems, non-intelligent computer-based versions, and traditional classroom instruction. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- Moreau, N. A. (2019). *Do clickers open minds? Use of a questioning strategy in developmental mathematics* (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University).
- Norton, P., & Hathaway, D. (2015). In search of a teacher education curriculum: Appropriating a design lens to solve problems of practice. *Educational technology*, 3-14.

- Noyes, A., & Sealey, P. (2012). Investigating participation in Advanced level mathematics: a study of student drop-out. *Research Papers in Education*, 27(1), 123-138.
- Papadakis, S., & Kalogiannakis, M. (Eds.). (2019). *Mobile learning applications in early childhood education*. IGI Global.
- Park, H. S. (2018). The impact of technology use on Hispanic students' mathematics achievement within family and school contexts: Subgroup analysis between English-and non-English-speaking students. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 38(4), 453-468.
- Pelgrum, W. J. (2001). Obstacles to the integration of ICT in education: results from a worldwide educational assessment. *Computers & education*, 37(2), 163-178.
- Prensky, M. R. (2012). *From digital natives to digital wisdom: Hopeful essays for 21st century learning*. Corwin Press.
- Razak, A. A., Connolly, T., & Hainey, T. (2012). Teachers' views on the approach of digital games-based learning within the curriculum for excellence. *International Journal of Game-Based Learning (IJGBL)*, 2(1), 33-51.
- Rosen, Y., & Beck-Hill, D. (2012). Intertwining digital content and a one-to-one laptop environment in teaching and learning: Lessons from the time to know program. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 44(3), 225-241.
- Ross, S. M., Morrison, G. R., & Lowther, D. L. (2010). Educational technology research past and present: Balancing rigor and relevance to impact school learning. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 1(1), 17-35.
- Silva, P. (2015). Davis' technology acceptance model (TAM)(1989). *Information seeking behavior and technology adoption: Theories and trends*, 205-219.
- Squire, K. D. (2013). *Gameplay in context: Learning through participation in communities of civilization III players*. Unpublished PhD thesis. Instructional Systems Technology Department, Indiana University.
- Subramanya, S. R., & Farahani, A. (2012). Point-of-View Article on: Design of a Smartphone App for Learning Concepts in Mathematics and Engineering. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 4(3), 173-184.